

Two new *Agapanthia* Audinet-Serville, 1835 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Kazakhstan

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Abstract. Two similar new species are described from East Kazakhstan *Agapanthia (Eopotes) kucherai* **sp. n.** (Lepsy environs) and *A. (E.) klabusayi* **sp. n.** (Shubarkayin environs). Color photos of specimens and photos of localities are proposed.

Introduction

Two new species described below belong to the same species-group of the subgenus *Eopotes* Gistel, 1857, as 2 species described by me from Kazakhstan recently (Danilevsky, 2024): *Agapanthia plewai* Danilevsky, 2024 and *A. badenkoi* Danilevsky, 2024, because both with red basal parts of 3rd-12th antennal joints and without setae tufts of 3rd antennal joints; but both have yellow elytra with dense elytral cover, partially hiding punctation, while elytra of two following new species look very dark, nearly black.

Acronyms of collections:

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia)

MH - collection of M. Holomčík (Lužice, Czech Republic)

FK - collection of F. Klabusay (Brno, Czech Republic)

KH - collection of K. Hodek (Brno, Czech Republic)

PK - collection of P. Kučera (Liberec, Czech Republic)

Results

Agapanthia kuchera sp. n.

Figs. 1-7

Description. Body small and narrow; frons elongated, shining, with several scattered small dots and very fine microsculpture, with pale recumbent pubescence concentrated near eyes, with several erect setae; genae a little shorter than lower eye lobes; vertex with a row of dense seta and hardly distinct small punctation; antennae thin, surpassing elytral apex in males with 5 joints, in females - with 3-4 joints; 3rd-12th joints red with black apices; antennal setae tufts are absent; apex of 3rd antennal joint with several single long setae (Fig. 3), which can be more or less denser (Fig. 4); apex of 4th antennal joint with not more than 3-5 long setae (Figs. 3-4); male prothorax about as wide posteriorly as long, in females prothorax basally a little wider than long; pronotum with dense central and lateral yellow stripes, without recumbent pubescence in between; pronotal punctation sparser in some places; elytra grey-black with poor luster; curved elytral margin with dense yellow pubescence; elytral setae patches hardly visible, nearly indistinct; grey lateral elytral stripe is absent; erect elytral setae short, strongly oblique, male elytra about 2.9 times longer than wide, female elytra - about 3.1-3.2 times; ventral body side with dense yellow pubescence; body length in males: 12.2-18 mm, body length in females: 12-18.1 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very close to *A. klabusayi* sp. n. described below, but differs by shorter and sparser frontal pubescence; shorter antennae, surpassing elytra with 5 (males) or 3-4 (females) joints; apical setae of 3rd antennal joints from single to less numerous; prothorax subquadrate (not transverse); pronotal punctation sparser in some places; elytral punctation finer and sparser, never conjugated; erect elytral setae shorter, less numerous, strongly oblique.

Material. Holotype, male, E Kazakhstan, Lepsy environs, 46°13'N, 78°58'E, 400 m, 2.6.2016, K. Hodek leg. - MD; 60 paratypes: 3 males, 2 females with the same label - MD; 32 males, 20 females with the same label - KH; 2 males, 1 female with the same data, P. Kučera leg. - PK.

Fig. 1. Holotype of *Agapanthia kucherai* sp. n.

Fig. 2. Paratype, female of *A. kucherai* sp. n.

Figs. 3-4. 2nd-4th antennal joints of *A. kucherai* sp. n.: 3 - male, 4 - female.

Figs. 5-6. *A. kucherai* sp. n. in nature on *Eremurus anderiensis*.

Fig. 7. Landscape of the type locality of *A. kucherai* sp. n. with *Eremurus anderiensis*.

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Biology. All specimens were observed feeding on *Eremurus inderiensis* (M. Bieb.) Regel. imagoes are active in early summer.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to P. Kučera, who took part in the collecting of the type series.

***Agapanthia klabusayi* sp. n.**

Figs 8-12

Description. Body small and narrow; frons elongated, shining, with several scattered small dots and very fine microsculpture, with very dense pale recumbent pubescence concentrated near eyes, with numerous erect setae; genae a little shorter than lower eye lobes; vertex with very distinct bigger punctation, micro-rugose, with a row of dense setae; antennae thin, surpassing elytral apex with 6 joints, in females - with 3 joints; 3rd-12th joints red with black apices; antennal setae tufts are absent; apex of 3rd antennal joint with several long setae (Figs 10-11); apex of 4th antennal joint with about 10 long setae; male prothorax slightly transverse, about 1.1 times shorter than basal width; in females prothorax about 1.3 times shorter than basal width; pronotum with dense central and lateral yellow stripes, without recumbent pubescence in between; pronotal punctation very dense, partly conjugated; elytra grey-black with poor luster; curved elytral margin with dense yellow pubescence; elytral setae patches hardly visible, nearly indistinct; grey lateral elytral stripe is absent; erect elytral setae longer, more numerous, less oblique, almost perpendicular; male elytra about 3 times longer than basal width, female elytra - about 2.9 times; ventral body side with dense yellow pubescence; body length in males: 12.0-17.9 mm, body length in females: 14.0-18.0 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very close to *A. kucherai* sp. n. described above, but differs by shorter and sparser frontal pubescence; shorter antennae, surpassing elytra with 5 (males) or 3-4 (females) joints; apical setae of 3rd antennal joints from single to less numerous; prothorax transverse; pronotal punctation sparse in places; elytral punctation finer and sparser, never conjugated; erect elytral setae shorter, less numerous, strongly oblique.

Fig. 8. Holotype of *Agapanthia klabusayi* sp. n.

Fig. 9. Paratype, female of *Agapanthia klabusayi* sp. n.

Fig. 10-11. 2nd-4th antennal joints of *A. klabusayi* sp. n.: 10 - male, 11 - female.

Fig. 12. Landscape of the type locality of *A. klabusayi* sp. n. with *Dictamnus* sp.

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Material. Holotype male, E Kazakhstan, 4 km E of Shubarkayin (Samarka), 49°08'42"N, 83°20'16"E, 810 m, 15.6.2024, K. Hodek leg. - MD; 74 paratypes: 1 male, 1 female with the same label - MD; 21 males, 6 females with the same label - KH; 14 males, 9 females with the same data, M.Holomčík leg. - MH; 14 males, 8 females with the same data, F. Klabusay leg. - FK.

Biology. All specimens were observed feeding on *Dictamus* sp. in the middle of June.

Etymology. The new taxon is dedicated to F. Klabusay, who took part in the collecting of the type series.

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